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Adina Camelia Bleotu, Lyn Tieu, Gabriela Bîlbîie, Mara Panaitescu, Anton Benz & Andreea Cristina Nicolae

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Disjunction across polarities: Scope versus strengthening in children's interpretations of negative disjunctive sentences

Adina Camelia Bleotu ^f

^aUniversity of Bucharest, Romania; ^bUniversity of Vienna, Austria; ^cUniversity of Toronto, Canada; ^dWestern Sydney University (MARCS Institute), Australia; ^eMacquarie University, Australia; ^fLeibniz-Zentrum Allgemeine Sprachwissenschaft (ZAS), Berlin, Germany

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the sources of the possible interpretations of negative disjunctive statements (e.g. *Girafa nu a cules ghiocelul sau trandafirul* 'The giraffe did not pick the snowdrop or the rose') in Romanian children and adults. Previous research highlights cross-linguistic variation among adults: English-speaking adults allow both *neither nor* and *not both* interpretations, while Japanese-speaking adults only allow the *not both* interpretation. In contrast, children across a number of languages have been shown to prefer the stronger *neither nor* interpretation. We attempt to connect this area of research with studies showing that children interpret positive disjunctive statements (e.g. *Girafa a cules ghiocelul sau trandafirul* 'The giraffe picked the snowdrop or the rose') in an inclusive or conjunctive manner (and in particular with studies that argue that the conjunctive interpretation is the result of scalar strengthening). If the source of strong meanings across polarities is strengthening, then we expect the same children who prefer *neither nor* interpretations of negative disjunctive statements to be the same children who prefer conjunctive interpretations of positive disjunctive statements. We conducted a Truth Value Judgment Task (TVJT) with Romanian 5-year-old children and a group of adult controls to examine their behavior in negative and positive disjunctive statements and to investigate a possible positive correlation between strong interpretations across sentence polarities. Our results indicate that both groups behaved relatively similarly: in negative contexts, they predominantly favored the *neither nor* interpretation, while in positive contexts, they predominantly favored an inclusive interpretation. These results do not support a positive correlation between strong interpretations of positive and negative disjunctive statements. Instead, we argue that strong interpretations may have different sources in sentences of differing polarity, namely, strengthening in positive statements and scope in negative ones.

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1. Introduction

The current study addresses the question of how Romanian 5-year-olds and adults interpret negative disjunctive sentences such as (1):

- (1) Girafa **nu** a cules ghiocelul **sau** trandafirul.
giraffe.DEF NEG has picked snowdrop.DEF or rose.DEF
'The giraffe did not pick the snowdrop or the rose.'

CONTACT Adina Camelia Bleotu Leibniz-Zentrum Allgemeine Sprachwissenschaft (ZAS), Berlin, Germany

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Logically, such configurations allow for three possible interpretations, as illustrated in (2) for English: (i) a strong *neither nor* interpretation (2a), (ii) a weaker *not both* interpretation (2b), and (iii) an additional strong *only one* interpretation (2c). The three interpretations have generally been argued to arise from the interaction of disjunction (which can be interpreted inclusively or exclusively) and the relative scope of negation and the disjunction. The strong *neither nor* interpretation arises when negation scopes over an inclusive disjunction, represented by the logical form $\neg(A \vee B) \equiv \neg A \wedge \neg B$, meaning neither disjunct is true. The weaker *not both* interpretation, represented by $\neg A \vee \neg B$, arises when negation is interpreted as scoping below the disjunction, logically excluding the possibility of both disjuncts being true. Lastly, the strong *only one* interpretation involves an exclusive (strengthened) wide scope disjunction, with the form $(\neg A \vee \neg B) \wedge \neg(\neg A \wedge \neg B)$, indicating exactly one disjunct is true.¹

- (2) The giraffe did **not** pick the snowdrop **or** the rose.
- (a) *neither nor*: The giraffe picked neither.
 - (b) *not both*: The giraffe didn't pick both: either only one or neither.
 - (c) *only one*: It is only one of the two that the giraffe did not pick.

Previous cross-linguistic research on negative disjunctive sentences has argued that languages differ in terms of which interpretations are allowed for such configurations, both for adults and for children. We ask which interpretations are obtained in child and adult Romanian, a language in which the interaction between negation and disjunction has been investigated only briefly and only in adult language (Lungu et al. 2021). Furthermore, we compare positive and negative disjunctive sentences to ascertain what, if any, relationship exists between the interpretations of these potentially ambiguous sentences (for a similar study in French, see Cochard et al. 2023). Similarly to the ambiguity of the negative sentences presented above, positive disjunctive sentences have also been shown to give rise to multiple interpretations, as illustrated in (3): (i) a weak inclusive interpretation (3a), (ii) a strong exclusive interpretation (3b), and (iii) a strong conjunctive interpretation (3c). In line with previous studies (such as Tieu et al. 2017; Huang and Crain 2020; Skordos et al. 2020, a.o.), we adopt clear definitions for inclusive, exclusive, and conjunctive interpretations. An inclusive interpretation is true both when only one of the disjuncts holds and when both of the disjuncts hold; the exclusive interpretation is true when only one disjunct is true, but false when both disjuncts are true; the conjunctive interpretation is true only when both disjuncts are true.²

- (3) The giraffe picked the snowdrop **or** the rose.
- (a) *Inclusive*: The giraffe picked one, possibly both.
 - (b) *Exclusive*: The giraffe picked only one, not both.
 - (c) *Conjunctive*: The giraffe picked both, not just one.

The comparison across polarities will enable us to determine whether there is a correlation between the types of interpretations children assign to disjunction in positive sentences and those that they assign in negative sentences.

The paper is structured as follows. In Sections 2 and 3, we present the relevant background on disjunction in positive and negative sentences in child and adult language; we also delve into the question of what the sources of available interpretations are. In Section 4, we discuss previous experimental work on disjunction in Romanian. Section 5 presents the experiment we conducted with Romanian-speaking children and adults. We discuss our main findings in Section 6, and conclude in Section 7.

¹As will be discussed later in the paper, there are alternative ways to derive some of these interpretations.

²Thus, while both inclusive and exclusive children may accept disjunctive utterances when one disjunct holds, only inclusive children (but not exclusive children) should accept them in scenarios where both disjuncts hold. Moreover, while both inclusive and conjunctive participants should accept disjunctive utterances in scenarios in which both disjuncts are true, only inclusive participants (and not conjunctive ones) should accept them when only one disjunct is true.

2. The Interpretation Of Positive Disjunctive Statements

2.1. The empirical landscape

Research on disjunction in child and adult language identifies three interpretations of disjunctive, statements: inclusive, exclusive, and conjunctive, as illustrated above in (3). Studies have shown that adults access inclusive and exclusive interpretations for simple forms of disjunction such as *or*, but tend to interpret complex disjunctions such as *either . . . or* exclusively (Nicolae and Sauerland 2016; Spector 2014; Bleotu et al. 2025c; Nicolae et al. 2024). In contrast, children have been shown to interpret both simple and complex forms of disjunction inclusively or conjunctively, but rarely exclusively (Paris 1973; Braine and Romain 1981; Singh et al. 2016; Tieu et al. 2017; Sauerland and Yatsushiro 2018; Huang and Crain 2020; Skordos et al. 2020; Bleotu et al. 2024a, 2025c). Nonetheless, exclusivity rates can vary, and in particular can be higher in experiments in which the relevant conjunctive alternatives are made more salient, e.g., through a question such as *Did the hen push the bus and the airplane?* (Bleotu et al. 2025a; Bhaumik 2025) or when the experimental task is action-based, e.g., involving coloring (Bleotu et al. 2025b).

2.2. Positive disjunctive statements: sources of possible interpretations

Adults' inclusive interpretation of disjunction is assumed to correspond to the logical interpretation of disjunction, while the exclusive interpretation is considered to arise from a scalar implicature. Scalar implicatures are traditionally viewed as pragmatic inferences that arise from assuming that language users adhere to the Maxim of Quantity: specifically, the submaxim "Make your contribution as informative as required" (Grice 1975). When a speaker uses a weaker term like *or* instead of the stronger conjunctive alternative *and*, hearers can be led to infer that the stronger alternative cannot be true, for otherwise the speaker would have used it instead. This pragmatic reasoning underlies the exclusive *A or B, but not both* interpretation of 'A or B'. Neo-Gricean accounts (e.g., Horn 1972; Gazdar 1979; Levinson 2000) treat this strengthening as a default inference linked to lexical scales (e.g., *(and, or)*), though they acknowledge that it can be cancelled in appropriate contexts. According to the grammatical approach to scalar implicatures (Chierchia et al. 2012), the exclusive interpretation of disjunction arises from applying a covert exhaustification operator *exh* (akin to a silent *only*), which has the result of negating the stronger conjunctive alternative and conjoining this negated alternative with the original proposition. In the case of a positive, unembedded, disjunction (4), the set of alternatives (*Alt*) is as given in (4a), and the result of applying exhaustification (*exh*) is as shown in (4b).

- (4) The giraffe picked the snowdrop **or** the rose.
 (a) *Alt* (The giraffe picked the snowdrop or the rose) =
 {The giraffe picked the snowdrop and the rose}³
 (b) *exh*[The giraffe picked the snowdrop or the rose] =
 The giraffe picked the snowdrop or the rose and the giraffe didn't pick the snowdrop and the rose
 = The giraffe picked the snowdrop or the rose but not both

Turning now to children, their preference for inclusive interpretations aligns with Noveck's (2001) proposal that they are more logical than adults. The source of their conjunctive interpretations (i.e., the *both, not just one* interpretation in (3c)), on the other hand, is a matter of some debate. Some have argued that conjunctive interpretations are a type of strengthened interpretation (Singh et al. 2016; Tieu et al. 2017), others that disjunctions are ambiguous between disjunctive and conjunctive interpretations (Sauerland and Yatsushiro 2018; Bleotu et al. 2024b), and still others have argued that this interpretation does not have a grammatical source, but rather reflects an experimental artifact (Skordos et al. 2020; Huang and Crain 2020).

³As mentioned below, the full set of alternatives includes the disjunction itself, as well as each disjunct. We set these aside here for ease of readability.

In this paper, we will focus on the implicature account, according to which children are assumed to derive the conjunctive interpretation through recursive exhaustification (Singh et al. 2016). According to this account, unlike adults, who generate the alternatives $\{p, q, p \wedge q\}$, children do not access the conjunctive alternative. Instead, they only access the individual disjuncts, each with its own implicatures, as alternatives. Recursive exhaustification amounts to the negation of these pre-exhaustified alternatives, that is, of the alternatives: $p \wedge \neg q$ (*only p*) and $q \wedge \neg p$ (*only q*). The negation of these stronger alternatives, together with the basic disjunctive meaning, results in a conjunctive interpretation, as shown in (5b).

- (5) The giraffe picked the snowdrop **or** the rose.
- (a) *Alt* (The giraffe picked the snowdrop or the rose) = {The giraffe picked only the snowdrop, The giraffe picked only the rose}
- (b) *exh*[The giraffe picked the snowdrop or the rose] = The giraffe picked the snowdrop or the rose and it is not the case that the giraffe picked only the snowdrop and it is not the case that the giraffe picked only the rose
= The giraffe picked the snowdrop and the rose

Moving now beyond plain disjunctive statements, we turn to the interaction between negation and disjunction, which can offer new insights into the interpretive strategies used by both children and adults.

3. The Interaction Between Negation And Disjunction

3.1. The empirical landscape

Here, we briefly describe the main findings from previous studies of negative disjunctive sentences. The way that adults interpret negative disjunctive sentences varies across languages, as noted by several researchers (Szabolcsi 2002; Goro and Akiba 2004; Goro 2007, 2015, 2017; Crain 2012; Shimada 2014; Pagliarini et al. 2018, 2021; Pagliarini, Reyes, et al. 2021; Lungu et al. 2021; Ličá 2024). Recall the possible interpretations for such sentences, repeated in (6):

- (6) The giraffe did **not** pick the snowdrop **or** the rose.
- (a) *Neither nor*: The giraffe picked neither.
- (b) *Not both*: The giraffe didn't pick both: either only one or neither.
- (c) *Only one*: It is only one of the two that the giraffe did not pick.

For adults (in languages such as English, German, French, Greek, Romanian, Bulgarian, and Korean), such sentences have been argued to have the *neither nor* interpretation; in contrast, in languages such as Japanese, Mandarin Chinese, Hungarian, Russian, Serbo-Croatian, Slovak, and Polish, adults have been reported to access the *not both* interpretation (Goro and Akiba 2004; Szabolcsi 2002).

Turning to acquisition, children across languages have been reported to interpret negative disjunctive statements like (6) as expressing the strong *neither nor* reading. Goro and Akiba (2004) report that Japanese children systematically rejected negative disjunctive statements in contexts where only one of the disjuncts was false, in line with a *neither nor* interpretation. Similar patterns of responses have been reported for children in Mandarin Chinese (Crain et al. 2013), in Turkish (Geckin et al. 2016), and in English, Dutch, French, Italian, and Catalan (Pagliarini et al. 2018, 2021; Pagliarini, Reyes, et al. 2021; Jasbi et al. 2023). Notably, children exhibit a robust preference for the stronger *neither nor* interpretation even in languages and contexts where adults permit (or even prefer) weaker readings.

3.2. Negative disjunctive statements: sources of possible interpretations

3.2.1. A scope account

The cross-linguistic variation observed in adults' interpretation of negative disjunctive sentences has been attributed to a Disjunction Parameter (Szabolcsi 2002; Goro 2007; Crain 2012), whereby

disjunction is marked as scoping above negation in certain languages but under negation in others. Note that the strong *neither nor* interpretation corresponds to the $[->V]$ scopal configuration, and the *not both* interpretation to the $[V>-]$ scopal configuration, as shown in (7).

(7) Possible interpretations of negative disjunctive sentences

- | | | |
|-----|--|--------------------|
| (a) | $\neg p \vee \neg q$ | <i>Not both</i> |
| (b) | $\neg(p \vee q) \equiv \neg p \wedge \neg q$ | <i>Neither nor</i> |

In languages where only the weak *not both* interpretation is allowed, namely where disjunction cannot scope under the negation, the disjunction has been said to be a positive polarity item (PPI). In the context of the Disjunction Parameter, such languages have been labeled as [+PPI], and the others as [-PPI]. Importantly, as Goro (2007: 180) stipulates, a [-PPI] disjunction may not undergo covert scope shifting. This means that the disjunction must remain in situ and cannot take scope above the negation, resulting in a conjunctive interpretation (the *neither nor* reading) in negative contexts, as observed in English.

As for children, they seem to prefer the *neither nor* interpretation cross-linguistically. According to Goro and Akiba (2004), there is a fundamental scopal difference between how Japanese children and Japanese adults interpret negative disjunctive statements involving negation and disjunctive direct objects, such as *John didn't eat ice cream or cake*. While children accept negative sentences with disjunctive direct objects only when neither disjunct is true, adults accept such sentences in contexts where only one disjunct is true. Goro and Akiba (2004) attribute this difference to the fact that Japanese adults assign obligatory wide scope to the disjunction (*or > not*), yielding the weaker interpretation in (7a), while Japanese children assign a narrow scope to the disjunction (*not > or*), yielding the stronger interpretation in (7b).

Notice that the weaker *not both* interpretation (i.e., *It is ice cream or cake that John didn't eat*) is in theory compatible with a situation in which neither disjunct is true. In order to explain why adults accept negative sentences with disjunctive direct objects only when one disjunct is false and not when both are false (Goro and Akiba 2004), one can take the further step of assuming that once adults have wide-scoped the disjunction above negation, they can subsequently strengthen the disjunction to an exclusive interpretation (i.e., *It is only the ice cream or only the cake that John didn't eat*). This step of strengthening is not explicitly proposed by Goro and Akiba (2004), but it is consistent with their analysis and is supported by later work, such as Otani et al. (2020). If one did not assume strengthening to the exclusive interpretation (Otani et al. 2020), one would not be able to explain why Japanese adults reject the negative sentence when both disjuncts are false (as such a scenario would be compatible with a wide scope, inclusive interpretation of the disjunction). The exclusivity implicature for the negative disjunctive case would be entirely parallel to the positive case, strengthening the inclusive interpretation of the disjunction to an exclusive one, as exemplified schematically in (8):

- (8) $\neg p \vee \neg q$
 (a) $Alt(\neg p \vee \neg q) = \{\neg p \wedge \neg q\}$
 (b) $exh[\neg p \vee \neg q] = (\neg p \vee \neg q) \wedge \neg(\neg p \wedge \neg q)$
 $= (\neg p \wedge q) \vee (\neg q \wedge p)$

Turning now to children's preference for the stronger *neither nor* interpretation, one explanation has been the Semantic Subset Principle (SSP). Crain et al. (1994) originally proposed the SSP as a general learning principle that allows learners to avoid subset problems without negative evidence: when an ambiguous sentence has two possible interpretations, one which entails the other, the child learner first adopts the interpretation that makes the sentence true in the narrowest range of circumstances, namely the stronger reading. If the learner instead adopted the superset reading, which is true in a wider range of situations, there would be no positive evidence that could lead the

learner to revise their initial hypothesis, as any evidence for the subset reading would also be consistent with the superset reading.

A subsequent, more technical formulation of the SSP specific to the context of the Disjunction Parameter can be found in Goro (2007). As noted by Shimada and Goro (2020) (p.103, footnote 3), Goro's (2007) version of the SSP is a learning algorithm meant to explain how children acquire the target setting of the Disjunction Parameter without access to negative evidence. Goro assumes that when the disjunction appears within the syntactic scope of negation (i.e., within its c-command domain), children opt for the stronger *neither nor* interpretation (in line with Crain et al. 2002). Crucially for Goro, the interpretation is constrained by the c-command relation between negation and disjunction.

In the current study, we assume Goro's (2007) implementation of the SSP, taking the c-command relation between disjunction and negation as a core property of the scope account. Cross-linguistic studies provide compelling evidence for this syntactic sensitivity; for instance, Japanese-speaking children interpret the disjunction marker *ka* disjunctively when it appears in a position structurally higher than negation, but when it appears in the scope of negation, children access the *neither nor* interpretation (Shimada 2014; Shimada and Goro 2020; Shimada and Sano 2022). This structurally driven shift in interpretation (depending on syntactic position) constitutes core evidence for the Scope Account, revealing children's sensitivity to the hierarchical relation between negation and disjunction.

In the context of negative disjunctive statements, the SSP predicts that children will initially assign the [-PPI] value, with the negation taking scope over the disjunction, resulting in the stronger (subset) *neither nor* interpretation, which is verified only when both disjuncts are false. The alternative interpretation, where disjunction takes scope over negation, is true in a wider range of circumstances, including cases where only one of the disjuncts is false. The *neither nor* reading is the stronger, narrower interpretation, given that it asymmetrically entails the *not both* reading. Starting with the stronger reading thus allows the learner to avoid the subset problem.

This learnability problem underscores the SSP's role in guiding children toward initially restrictive interpretations. As they encounter positive evidence in [+PPI] languages, they can eventually reset the Disjunction Parameter to match adult interpretations, where disjunction takes scope over negation. This principle has the advantage of accounting for cross-linguistic patterns in the acquisition of negative disjunctive statements in the absence of negative evidence.⁴

As noted by Goro (2007) and Shimada and Goro (2020), the relevant evidence required to reset the value from [-PPI] to [+PPI] is exceedingly rare. In this respect, the SSP does not fully resolve the learnability challenge (see Sano et al. 2024; Shimada 2025), as it does not necessarily explain how children can reset the parameter value based solely on positive evidence, given the sparseness of such input. This raises the question of how children whose target language is [+PPI] are able to make this change. Thus, while the SSP can explain the acquisition process without the need for negative evidence, it does presuppose that the needed positive evidence is both available and sufficient for language acquisition, i.e., that every language learner whose target language conforms to the Japanese-type parameter (i.e., [+PPI]) can access a sufficient amount of the relevant positive evidence.

Moreover, another somewhat problematic consequence arising from embracing a scope account for negative disjunctive statements is that we end up with different ways of capturing children's interpretation of disjunctive sentences across polarities. Notably, much of the literature on positive disjunctive statements focuses on strengthening as an explanation for children's conjunctive interpretation of such utterances, while many studies investigating negative disjunctive statements focus on a scopal account, appealing to the syntactic scope relations between negation and disjunction. This divergence results in a non-unified theoretical landscape.

⁴Importantly, an SSP account in terms of c-command can also be extended to capture empirical findings regarding other types of sentences where logical operators interact, namely, children's preference for strong interpretations of sentences involving negation and universal quantifiers (*Everyone didn't ...* interpreted as *None did ...*, see Musolino and Lidz 2006), negation and epistemic modals (*possible ... not* interpreted as *impossible*, see Moscati and Crain 2014), and negation and deontic modals expressing lack of necessity (*needn't* interpreted as *mustn't*, see Bleotu, Benz, et al. 2023a).

3.2.2. A strengthening account

While scalar implicatures are generally robust in positive, upward-entailing contexts, they are argued to be much less available in negative or downward-entailing environments (e.g., Chierchia 2004, Panizza et al. 2009a, 2009b; Panizza and Chierchia 2011). For example, an English sentence such as *The giraffe didn't pick the snowdrop or the rose* is typically interpreted with negation scoping over disjunction (NEG > OR), yielding a literal *neither nor* interpretation. This reading is already strong and, thus, does not typically license further scalar strengthening.⁵ However, scalar implicature derivation is not blocked uniformly in all negated sentences; rather, it is sensitive to the monotonicity properties of the relevant scope domain. If the parse is OR > NEG (i.e., *The giraffe did not pick the snowdrop OR the giraffe did not pick the rose*), then the disjunction scopes over the local negation, and the relevant domain is upward-entailing. In such contexts, implicature derivation should, in principle, be possible. Strengthening this interpretation via an exhaustivity operator would yield the inference: *The giraffe didn't pick the snowdrop or didn't pick the rose, but the giraffe did pick one of the two*, as shown in (9).

- (9) $\neg p \vee \neg q$
 (a) $Alt(\neg p \vee \neg q) = \{\neg p \wedge \neg q\}$
 (b) $exh[\neg p \vee \neg q] = (\neg p \vee \neg q) \wedge \neg(\neg p \wedge \neg q)$
 $= (\neg p \vee \neg q) \wedge (p \vee q)$

Only in NEG > OR configurations, then, is the context genuinely downward-entailing and thus unfavorable to implicatures. In contrast, OR > NEG configurations provide an upward-entailing environment for the disjunction and therefore are not subject to the same constraint. Depending on whether strengthening is invoked, the wide scope interpretation of disjunction could thus yield two possibilities: the equivalent of an inclusive (unstrengthened) interpretation, which would amount to *not both*, or the equivalent of an exclusive (strengthened) interpretation, which would amount to *only one*.

Following this logic, strengthening could potentially also arise in child language. Otani et al. (2020), Shimada and Goro (2020), and Cocharde et al. (2023) discuss the possibility of a strengthening account for children's interpretation of negative disjunctive statements. They argue that the *neither nor* interpretation could be seen as the result of strengthening, similar to how the conjunctive interpretation of disjunction in positive contexts has been argued to be the result of strengthening. According to this possibility, the source for children's *neither nor* interpretation is not the narrow scope of disjunction with respect to negation, but rather the application of recursive exhaustification to a wide scope disjunction. Children construct a set of preexhaustified alternatives (*only $\neg p$, only $\neg q$*), and strengthen the inclusive interpretation of the negative disjunctive statement by conjoining the given proposition with the negation of these pre-exhaustified alternatives, as shown schematically in (10). The result is a strong interpretation consisting of the conjunction of the two negated disjuncts, the steps of which we outline below.

- (10) $\neg p \vee \neg q$
 (a) $Alt(\neg p \vee \neg q) = \{\neg p \wedge q, \neg q \wedge p\}$
 (b) $exh[\neg p \vee \neg q] = (\neg p \vee \neg q) \wedge \neg(\neg p \wedge q) \wedge \neg(\neg q \wedge p)$
 $= \neg p \wedge \neg q$

As argued by Shimada and Goro (2020), exploring whether the source of children's *neither nor* interpretations of negative disjunctive statements is strengthening rather than scope is important, given that, if it turns out to be so, a unified account for why children prefer strong interpretations in both positive and negative statements would be possible.

⁵An alternative interpretation, where an exhaustivity operator applies under negation (NEG > EXH > OR), has been proposed in instances where the connective is focused, yielding a reading equivalent to *either neither or both*. However, this reading is usually prosodically marked, and was also not observed in our experimental data. As such, we set it aside in the current study.

Several recent studies have taken up this path either theoretically or empirically. Pagliarini et al. (2018) discuss the possibility of extending the strengthening account from positive to negative sentences but reject it based on several empirical issues. One of their most striking arguments against this possibility is that we generally observe a higher proportion of children who access a *neither nor* interpretation of negative disjunctive statements than of children who access a conjunctive interpretation of positive disjunctive statements. However, as pointed out by Shimada and Goro (2020), it is difficult to directly compare results across studies, which involve different experimental designs and groups of participants. Our study will overcome this issue by adopting a within-subject design, allowing us to investigate participants' interpretations of both positive and negative disjunctive sentences within the same experiment.

Otani et al. (2020) approach the possibility of extending strengthening to negative disjunctive sentences by testing whether, similarly to the findings in Skordos et al. (2020) for positive disjunctive sentences, children become inclusive in their interpretation of disjunction under negation in the presence of a third pictured alternative, i.e., when the context contains not just the two objects mentioned in the disjunctive statement, but also a third object. With this objective in mind, Otani et al. (2020) tested Japanese children in a follow-up experiment to Goro and Akiba (2004)'s study, presenting visual contexts that contained three alternatives instead of just two. However, while the presence of a third alternative has been shown to affect children's interpretation of positive disjunctive statements (i.e., children appear to become more inclusive and less conjunctive), this manipulation did not seem to have any effect on children's interpretation of negative disjunctive statements: Otani et al.'s child participants still adopted the *neither nor* interpretation. This finding was taken by the authors to suggest that children's strong interpretations of positive and negative disjunctive statements have different sources: while the conjunctive interpretation is due to strengthening, as proposed by Singh et al. (2016), the *neither nor* interpretation is due to the narrow scope of disjunction with respect to negation, as proposed by Goro (2007).

Another recent study by Shimada and Goro (2020) also takes up the question of whether Japanese-speaking preschoolers *neither nor* interpretations are due to strengthening. These authors investigate disjunctive noun phrases in different syntactic positions, namely in accusative-marked objects (Experiment 1), nominative-marked subjects (Experiment 2), and nominative-marked objects (Experiment 3). The authors reason that there should be no difference in interpretation among children in the three experiments, if the source of their interpretation is strengthening, given that strengthening is, in principle, unaffected by the syntactic position of the disjunctive phrase. The results indicate that children accessed a *neither nor* interpretation in Experiment 1, but not in Experiments 2 and 3. The authors take these findings to suggest that the *neither nor* interpretation of disjunction cannot be due to strengthening, and instead attribute it to non-adult-like scope assignment.

Recently, Cochard et al. (2023) also discussed the possibility of a strengthening source for *neither nor*, based on a study where French-speaking children and adults had to judge both positive and negative disjunctive statements (in a within-subjects design). They propose that children who retrieve the full set of alternatives with plain OR will also do so with OR > NOT. Note that children who are conjunctive with positive disjunctive statements could have either a [+PPI] or a [-PPI] grammar when interpreting negative disjunctive statements. While a child with a [-PPI] grammar would access the *neither nor* interpretation of negative disjunctive statements by virtue of OR being interpreted in the scope of negation, a child with a [+PPI] grammar would derive the *neither nor* interpretation via double exhaustification of an OR > NOT parse, assuming that they fail to access the conjunctive alternative. Thus, conjunctive children should only allow *neither nor* interpretations. This prediction seems to be confirmed by their experimental findings: notably, conjunctive children never exhibited exclusive readings in negative contexts.

Given the mixed findings in the previous literature, further investigation of other languages is needed in order to shed light on whether children rely on the same interpretive mechanisms in negative and positive disjunctive statements.

4. Disjunction In Romanian

In a cross-linguistic acceptability judgment study conducted with adult speakers of French, Italian, Romanian, and English, Lungu et al. (2021) presented participants with sentences like (11), crossing Scope (*wide, narrow*) and Downward Entailing (DE) item (*negation, without, other DE*), and asked participants to rate the naturalness of continuations of these sentences, such as (11a) and (11b).

- (11) If I remember correctly, Mary **didn't** invite John **or** Suzi to her birthday party.
 (a) Narrow scope continuation: She's upset with both of them and doesn't want to see them.
 (b) Wide scope continuation: I don't know which of them.
 (Lungu et al. 2021, 223)

Following Szabolcsi (2002), in [+PPI] languages (French and Italian) the wide scope continuation should be preferred, while in [-PPI] languages (English and Romanian) the narrow scope continuation should be favored. However, the experimental results suggest that this distinction is not as clear-cut as previously believed, challenging the binary classification associated with the Disjunction Parameter. In English, for instance, both continuations are possible, with a preference for the narrow scope continuation. In Romanian, both continuations are also possible, but with a slight preference for the wide scope continuation. These findings undermine the idea of a clear-cut binary classification of languages into [+PPI] and [-PPI], suggesting that PPI-hood may be a matter of degree. They also allow for the possibility that disjunctions may undergo covert scope shifting, calling into question Goro's (2007) claim to the contrary. Moreover, our findings will suggest that Romanian might be at an intermediate point between [+PPI] and [-PPI], rather than being a clear [-PPI] language.

In an attempt to settle whether Romanian and English are similar with respect to the interaction between negation and disjunction, Lică (2024) employed a question-after-story task, exemplified in (12), in order to investigate adult speakers' interpretation of negative disjunctive statements in Romanian L1, English L1 and English L2-Romanian L1. The design crossed scenario type (a scenario where neither disjunct was true versus a scenario where one of the disjuncts was true) and negative statement type (containing *nici ... nici* 'neither ... nor' versus *nu ... sau* 'not ... or').

- (12) Bibi tells us a story:
 One day I was at the market with Jenny. A mouse who is friends with Jenny saw us and came over. Jenny bought a carrot, an onion. Jenny asked the mouse to put them in the bag while she went to the bakery. Then, Jenny left. While Jenny was at the bakery ...
 (a) ... the mouse decided that he wanted to put only one vegetable in the bag. (*1 Disjunct-True Scenario*)
 (b) ... the mouse decided not to put any vegetable in the bag. (*None Scenario, i.e., 0-Disjunct-True Scenario*)
 Jenny returns but she doesn't know what happened. She says:
Soarecele nu a pus morcovul sau ceapa în pungă.
 'The mouse didn't put the carrot or the onion in the bag.'
 Is she right?

The results indicate that the English speakers preferred the [-PPI] *neither nor* interpretation; they also accepted the weaker interpretation, but at much lower rates. The Romanian participants, on the other hand, allowed both readings and favored the [+PPI] *not both* interpretation. This finding challenges Szabolcsi's (2002) classification and aligns with the findings of Lungu et al.'s (2021) study.⁶

Regarding disjunction in child Romanian, recent studies by Bleotu et al. (2023a) and Bleotu et al. (2025c) examine Romanian children's interpretation of various forms of disjunction. These studies reveal that children are inclusive with the simple and complex versions of *sau*-based disjunctions (*sau* and *sau ... sau*), but inclusive and conjunctive with the complex disjunction *fie ... fie*. Importantly for our purposes, the interaction between negation and disjunction has not yet been investigated in child Romanian, a gap that will be addressed by the current study.

⁶L2 English-L1 Romanian speakers showed more variable behavior: while some displayed the L1 preference, suggesting transfer, others displayed a preference for the *neither nor* interpretation.

While Romanian exhibits a rich array of disjunctions (simple disjunctions, such as *sau* and *ori* ‘or’, as well as complex disjunctions such as *sau . . . sau*, *ori . . . ori*, and *fie . . . fie* ‘either . . . or’), the present study focuses on negative disjunctive sentences containing the simple disjunction *sau*. We chose not to examine negation in interaction with complex disjunctions or a prosodically marked form of the simple disjunction *sau* (which involves both disjuncts being stressed), given that these disjunctions typically scope above negation, and their use in negative disjunctive statements is quite marked in the adult grammar.

5. Current Experiment

5.1. Aim

In the current study, we test Romanian children’s behavior in both positive and negative disjunctive statements. The experiment was designed to investigate how the same participants respond to both positive and negative disjunctive statements and whether any patterns can be identified across polarities. While the varying interpretations of negative disjunctive statements can have multiple sources, including a scopal one, the different interpretations of positive disjunctive statements cannot be attributed to scope. The results can thus inform debates about the sources of the ambiguity of negative disjunctive sentences, by allowing us to compare behavior across polarities in both child and adult language.

5.2. Predictions

In the case of negative disjunctive statements, the results of Lungu et al. (2021) lead us to expect adults to access both the *neither nor* and the *not both* interpretations. However, if the Strongest Meaning Hypothesis (Dalrymple et al. 1998) is at play, adults might prefer strong over weak meanings, and, consequently, they might respond based on the *neither nor* interpretation more often. As for children, if they observe the Semantic Subset Principle (in the sense of Goro 2007), they should associate negative disjunctive statements only with the *neither nor* interpretation. However, if they are adult-like, they should access both interpretations.

In the case of positive disjunctive statements, previous studies (Bleotu et al. 2023, 2025c) lead us to expect adults to exhibit both inclusive and exclusive interpretations of the disjunction *sau*, while children are expected to interpret the disjunction inclusively, and sometimes conjunctively (Singh et al. 2016; Tieu et al. 2017).

Regarding the question of whether the same participants might exhibit strong interpretations of both the positive and negative disjunctive statements, we predict that if children’s source for the *neither nor* interpretation is strengthening rather than scope, then the children who strengthen in negative disjunctive statements may also strengthen in positive disjunctive statements, i.e., they will consistently apply the same strengthening mechanism across polarities. Strengthening in the positive cases could, in principle, lead to an exclusive or a conjunctive interpretation, but given that few studies have found exclusive behavior in children, we assume it is the conjunctive reading that is more likely to surface. Thus, the children who assign a *neither nor* interpretation to negated disjunction should also assign the *conjunctive* ‘both A and B’ reading to positive disjunctive statements. Note that the *conjunctive* reading here is not equivalent to the *inclusive* reading ‘A or B or possibly both’.

5.3. Participants

We collected data from 32 typically-developing monolingual Romanian-speaking 5-year-old children (age range: 5-6 years, $M=5;04$) and 40 adult native speaker controls. Children were recruited from Kindergartens No. 248 and No. 203 in Bucharest, while the adult participants were undergraduate students at the University of Bucharest.

5.4. Methodology and Materials

Task Following Tieu et al. (2017) and much subsequent work, we conducted a modified Truth Value Judgment Task (TVJT) presented in Prediction Mode rather than Description Mode (Singh et al. 2016). Such a task has the advantage of licensing ignorance inferences, which often characterize disjunctive statements. Participants were familiarized with situations containing a character that could carry out an action involving one or more pictured objects; they then had to judge a puppet's guesses about a potential outcome of the situation. Below we outline the three steps involved in each trial:

- (1) **FAMILIARIZATION:** participants were introduced to a character and four objects. The character was presented as somewhat moody: it sometimes did a certain action with one or several objects, but would sometimes choose not to do anything at all. They were told that the character could choose to do the action with one object, to do the action with several objects, or not to do the action at all.
- (2) **GUESS:** Bibi the puppet made a guess about what would happen.
- (3) **DECISION:** Participants then saw the outcome, and they had to say whether Bibi had guessed well.

The characters' moodiness was meant to encourage participants to envisage all the possible outcomes the situations could have, rather than imagining the characters necessarily performing an action with one or more objects.

Practice trials Participants were first presented with three practice trials, where the puppet made clearly true/clearly false non-disjunctive guesses (of the form *X acted upon object A / X did not act upon object A*) regarding various situations. The purpose of the practice phase was to familiarize participants with both true and false guesses, both positive and negative sentences, and with the different kinds of situations they might encounter in the experiment: those where the main character acted on one or both of the mentioned objects, as well as those in which the character chose not to do anything at all. The practice trials involved two positive non-disjunctive statements (one true, one false) and one negative non-disjunctive statement (true). For the true positive non-disjunctive statement, the character acted upon the mentioned object, while for the false positive non-disjunctive statement, the character did not act upon any object. For the true negative non-disjunctive statement, the character acted upon two objects instead of one.

Test trials The test phase consisted of 32 experimental trials (24 targets, 2 controls, 6 true/false fillers). The 24 targets involved 12 negative disjunctive sentences and 12 positive disjunctive sentences. Negative disjunctive sentences such as (13) were presented in: (i) 2-disjunct-true (2DT) contexts (x4), where both disjuncts were true (e.g., the giraffe picked both flowers), (ii) 1-disjunct-true (1DT) contexts (x4), where only one disjunct was true (e.g., the giraffe picked only the snowdrop), and (iii) 0-disjunct-true (0DT) contexts (x4), where neither disjunct was true (e.g., the giraffe picked neither of the flowers). [Table 1](#) provides an example of a negative disjunctive trial in the 2DT condition, where the character acted upon two objects. See [Appendix A1](#) and [A2](#) for examples of negative disjunctive trials in the 1DT and 0DT conditions, respectively.

- (13) Girafa **nu** a cules ghiocelul **sau** trandafirul.
giraffe.DEF NEG has picked snowdrop.DEF or rose.DEF
'The giraffe did not pick the snowdrop or the rose.'

Positive disjunctive sentences such as (14) were presented in: (i) 0-disjunct-true (0DT) contexts (x4), where neither disjunct was true (because the animal chose to do nothing), (ii) 1-disjunct-true (1DT) contexts (x4), where one disjunct was true (e.g., the hen pushed only the bus), and (iii) 2-disjunct-true (2DT) contexts (x4), where both disjuncts were true (e.g., the hen pushed both objects). [Table 2](#) provides an example of a positive disjunctive trial in the 1DT condition, where the character acted on a single object.

Table 1: Example of a negative disjunctive trial in the 2DT condition

2DT	Pictures
<p>SCENE 1: There once was a giraffe who sometimes picked flowers and sometimes did not. As she was walking, she saw some beautiful flowers. She could choose to pick a flower, she could choose to pick several flowers, she could choose to pick nothing. Let's see if Bibi can guess what happened next!</p>	
<p>SCENE 2: EXPERIMENTER: Bibi, tell us, what happened next? BIBI: <i>Girafa nu a cules ghiocelul sau trandafirul.</i> 'The giraffe did not pick the snowdrop or the rose.' EXPERIMENTER: Let's see if Bibi's right!</p>	
<p>SCENE 3 (following seeing a picture where the giraffe is holding both a snowdrop and a rose): Look, the giraffe picked this and this! Did Bibi guess well?</p>	

Table 2: Example of a positive disjunctive trial in the 1DT condition

1DT	Pictures
<p>SCENE 1: There once was a hen who sometimes pushed her toys, and sometimes did not. One day, her papa gave her four new toys: a bus, a car, a truck, and a plane. The hen could choose to push an object, could choose to push several, or could choose not to push anything. Let's see if Bibi can guess what happened next!</p>	
<p>SCENE 2: EXPERIMENTER: Bibi, tell us, what happened next? BIBI: <i>Găina a împins autobuzul sau avionul.</i> 'The hen pushed the bus or the plane.' EXPERIMENTER: Let's see if Bibi's right!</p>	
<p>SCENE 3 (following animation of hen pushing the bus down the hill): Look, the hen pushed this! Did Bibi guess well?</p>	

- (14) Găina a împins autobuzul **sau** barca.
hen.DEF has pushed bus.DEF or boat.DEF
'The hen pushed the bus or the boat.'

We also included a false control condition (x2), in which the hen pushed neither of the objects mentioned, but instead a different one. Participants also heard three fillers, which contained no disjunction. These five controls and fillers were included to ensure that participants understood and were paying attention to the task.

Importantly, to address the potential objection that children's conjunctive interpretation is an experimental artifact related to the number of objects in the context (Skordos et al. 2020; Huang and Crain 2020), we introduced additional objects in the background so that four objects were present, even though the test sentences only ever mentioned two.

5.5. Results

The data and scripts for the statistical analyses below are available at: https://osf.io/v9wt4/?view_only=2adb96956b7547d19acbed72552d4e75.

Only participants who correctly answered more than 50% of the fillers and controls were included in the analysis. This criterion led to the exclusion of two child participants. Figure 1 displays the percentage of *yes*-responses to the 0DT, 1DT and 2DT conditions across groups and polarities.

We fit a mixed-effects logistic regression model to the data, with Answer as a dependent variable (coded as 1 if the answer was *yes* and 0 otherwise), and Group (children vs. adults), Polarity (positive vs. negative), Context (0DT, 1DT, 2DT), and their three-way interaction as fixed effects. Random intercepts for Participant and Sentence were included. The model revealed main effects of Group ($\beta = -1.01$, $SE = 0.38$, $Z = -2.69$, $p = .007$), with adults generally saying *yes* more than children, and of Context, with fewer *yes*-answers in 1DT ($\beta = -3.38$, $SE = 0.32$, $Z = -10.40$, $p < .001$) and 2DT contexts ($\beta = -4.54$, $SE = 0.39$, $Z = -11.77$, $p < .001$) compared to 0DT. There was also a significant effect of Polarity, with negative polarity decreasing the likelihood of a *yes*-answer ($\beta = -6.29$, $SE = 0.65$, $Z = -9.72$, $p < .001$). Importantly, significant two- and three-way interactions were observed. Group interacted with Context (1DT: $\beta = 1.30$, $SE = 0.44$, $Z = 2.97$, $p = .003$; 2DT: $\beta = 1.74$, $SE = 0.50$, $Z = 3.49$, $p < .001$), and with Polarity (1DT: $\beta = 1.76$, $SE = 0.82$, $Z = 2.14$, $p = .032$). There was also a significant interaction between Context and Polarity (1DT: $\beta = 10.29$, $SE = 0.77$, $Z = 13.44$, $p < .001$; 2DT: $\beta = 10.45$, $SE = 0.77$, $Z = 13.63$, $p < .001$). The three-way interaction between Group, Context, and Polarity was significant as well (1DT: $\beta = -2.95$, $SE = 0.97$, $Z = -3.04$, $p = .002$; 2DT: $\beta = -2.28$, $SE = 0.98$, $Z = -2.32$, $p = .020$).

Follow-up pairwise comparisons of estimated marginal means revealed several significant differences. For example, in the negative condition, adults showed a significantly higher likelihood of *yes*-answers in the 0DT condition compared to both 1DT ($z = 10.40$, $p < .001$) and 2DT ($z = 11.77$, $p < .001$) conditions. Similarly, in the negative condition, children also demonstrated a significantly higher likelihood of *yes*-answers in the 0DT condition compared to the 1DT ($z = 6.90$, $p < .001$) and 2DT conditions ($z = 8.40$, $p < .001$). This pattern mirrors that of adults. Participants thus mostly accepted negative statements in the 0DT condition, but rejected them in the 1DT and 2DT conditions. In contrast, participants mostly rejected the positive statements in the 0DT condition, whereas they tended to accept them in the 1DT and 2DT conditions.

Figure 1: Proportion of *yes* answers per Group (children, adults), Sentence Polarity (positive, negative), and Context (0DT, 1DT, 2DT).

Next, we examined individual participants' response patterns more closely, using their responses to the different conditions to identify their interpretation of the disjunction. Let us first consider the positive sentences. Following Tieu et al. (2017), we considered inclusive, exclusive, and conjunctive interpretations to be the main interpretive patterns, which could be identified based on responses to the 0DT, 1DT, and 2DT conditions (Table 3). To these three categories, we also added the possibility of *mixed* and *inconsistent* participants. We thus classified participants as follows:

- **Inclusive:** accepted more than 50% of both 1DT and 2DT items, and rejected more than 50% of 0DT items
- **Exclusive:** accepted more than 50% of 1DT items, but fewer than 50% of 2DT items and fewer than 50% of 0DT items
- **Conjunctive:** accepted more than 50% of 2DT items, but fewer than 50% of 1DT items and fewer than 50% of 0DT items
- **Mixed:** accepted exactly 50% of either 1DT or 2DT items
- **Inconsistent:** showed patterns of responses inconsistent with the other categories

Table 3: Expected responses to 0DT, 1DT, and 2DT conditions depending on the interpretation of the disjunction (in positive sentences).

Interpretation	0DT	1DT	2DT
INCLUSIVE	No	Yes	Yes
EXCLUSIVE	No	Yes	No
CONJUNCTIVE	No	No	Yes

Table 4 displays the distribution of participants across the different interpretive categories for the positive disjunctive statements. Most participants (22/30 children, 28/40 adults) were inclusive, accepting the utterance in both 1DT and 2DT contexts more than 50% of the time (at least 3 out of 4 trials).

Table 4: Distribution of participants across the different interpretive categories (for positive disjunctive statements).

Groups	inclusive	exclusive	conjunctive	mixed	inconsistent
Children	22	1	2	3	2
Adults	28	6	2	4	0

Given that the inclusive interpretation was clearly the predominant pattern in the dataset, we next set out to determine whether there was a significant difference in how adults and children were distributed across inclusive vs. non-inclusive categories. To do so, we conducted a Fisher's Exact Test on the participant counts across the categories **Inclusive** vs. **Not inclusive** (which encompassed *exclusive*, *conjunctive*, *mixed*, and *inconsistent*). The test revealed that the response patterns between adults and children were not significantly different across these two categories ($p = 0.80$, *odds ratio* = 1.18, 95% *CI* [0.37, 3.94]).

Turning now to the negative disjunctive statements, we classified participants based on their responses to the 0DT, 1DT, and 2DT conditions as follows (see also Table 5):

- **Not both:** accepted more than 50% of 0DT and 1DT items, but fewer than 50% of 2DT items
- **Only one:** accepted more than 50% of 1DT items, but fewer than 50% of 0DT items and fewer than 50% of 2DT items
- **Neither nor:** accepted more than 50% of 0DT items, but fewer than 50% of 1DT and 2DT items
- **Mixed:** accepted exactly 50% of either 0DT, 1DT, or 2DT items
- **Inconsistent:** showed patterns of responses inconsistent with the other categories

Table 5: Categorization of participants in the negative disjunctive statements based on their responses in the 0DT, 1DT, and 2DT conditions.

Interpretation	0DT	1DT	2DT
NOT BOTH	Yes	Yes	No
ONLY ONE	No	Yes	No
NEITHER NOR	Yes	No	No

Table 6 displays the distribution of participants across the different interpretive categories for the negative disjunctive statements. 25/40 adults consistently opted for a *neither nor* interpretation, accepting negative disjunctive statements in the 0DT context and rejecting them in the 1DT and 2DT contexts. Additionally, 3/40 adults opted for the weaker *not both* interpretation (accepting the negative disjunctive statements in the 0DT and 1DT contexts, and rejecting them in the 2DT context), while 11/40 showed mixed behavior. Of the child participants, 14/30 consistently opted for a *neither nor* interpretation, 2/30 opted for a *not both* interpretation, 10/30 showed mixed behavior (4 of these 10 oscillated between *neither nor* and *not both* interpretations), and the remaining 4/30 gave inconsistent responses.

Table 6: Distribution of participants across the different interpretive categories (for negative disjunctive statements).

Groups	not both	only one	neither nor	mixed	inconsistent
Children	2	0	14	10	4
Adults	3	0	25	11	1

Given that the *neither nor* interpretation was the predominant pattern in the dataset, we next set out to determine whether adults and children were distributed differently across the **Neither** and **Not Neither** categories (which encompassed *not both*, *only one*, *mixed* and *inconsistent*), using a Fisher's Exact Test on the participant counts across the two categories. The test revealed that adults and children did not differ in their distribution across these categories ($p = 0.23$, *odds ratio* = 1.89, 95% *CI* [0.66, 5.56]).

Comparing the distribution of adults across interpretive categories for the positive and negative disjunctive statements, we observe that five out of six of the exclusive adults opted for a *neither nor* interpretation. In other words, almost all adults who opted for strengthening the disjunction to exclusivity in positive disjunctive statements also had a strong *neither nor* interpretation for the negative disjunctive statements. Of the 28 inclusive adults, 18 opted for a *neither nor* interpretation, two for a *not both* interpretation, seven for mixed interpretations (oscillating between *neither nor* and *not both*), and one was inconsistent. Comparing the distribution of adults for the negative disjunctive statements versus the positive disjunctive statements, we observe that of the 25 adults who opted for the *neither nor* interpretation, 18 were inclusive, six were exclusive and two were mixed. In other words, even adults who accessed the strong interpretation of disjunction in negative sentences did not always interpret the disjunction exclusively in positive sentences.

Turning to children, comparing the distribution of interpretation types in positive disjunctive statements to those in negative disjunctive statements, we observe that of the 22 inclusive children, 10 opted for a *neither nor* interpretation, two for a *not both* interpretation, six displayed a mixed pattern, and three were inconsistent. Of the five children who displayed the mixed pattern for the positive disjunctive statements, three also displayed the mixed pattern for the negative disjunctive statements, while one opted for *neither nor* and one was inconsistent. There were also two conjunctive children in the positive condition: one opted for *neither nor* in the negative condition, and the other displayed a mixed pattern. The one child who was exclusive in the positive condition also opted for the *neither nor* interpretation in the negative condition. Comparing the distribution of children across the negative disjunctive statements versus the positive disjunctive statements, of the 14 children who

Table 7: Distribution of child participants across the *Conjunctive* and *Non-conjunctive* categories (for positive disjunctive sentences) and *Neither* and *Not Neither* categories (for negative disjunctive sentences).

	Neither	Not Neither
Conjunctive	1	1
Non-conjunctive	12	16

opted for the *neither nor* interpretation, 10 were inclusive for the positive disjunctive statements, one was conjunctive, one was exclusive, one displayed a mixed pattern, and one was inconsistent. The two children who opted for the *not both* interpretation, and six of the 10 children who displayed the mixed pattern for the negative statements were inclusive for the positive statements.

To assess a possible association between conjunctive interpretations of the positive disjunctive statements and *neither nor* interpretations of the negative disjunctive statements in children, we carried out a Fisher's Exact Test on the distribution of children across the conjunctive and non-conjunctive categories of the positive conditions and the *neither* and *not neither* categories of the negative conditions (see Table 7), which revealed no evidence of an association ($p = 1$, *odds ratio* = 1.32, 95% *CI* [0.016, 111]).

6. Discussion

In this section, we discuss in further detail some notable aspects of our experimental findings.

6.1. The interpretation of positive disjunctive statements

The results of our experiment reveal that in positive disjunctive statements, both adults and children rarely derived scalar implicatures, showing an overall inclusive behavior. The children's responses are not surprising in light of prior work on implicatures in general (e.g., Noveck 2001) and on disjunction specifically (e.g., Paris 1973; Braine and Romain 1981; Tieu et al. 2017). The adult pattern of responses, however, is surprising given that adults are generally reported to derive implicatures in experiments similar to ours. We believe that the lower exclusivity rates in our experiment can be explained by a design aspect of our materials, notably that the background of the images contained additional objects to those mentioned in the disjunctive utterances.⁷

In a previous study involving positive disjunctive utterances and using the same guessing mode (Bleotu et al. 2025c), we compared adults' interpretations in two conditions: one with only the two mentioned objects present (2-Object Condition), and one with two additional, unmentioned objects (4-Object Condition). We found that adults were more likely to derive exclusive interpretations in the 2-Object Condition, while in the 4-Object Condition, responses were more inclusive. A similar pattern seems to have emerged in the present study, with adults showing low exclusivity rates with 4-object backgrounds. We interpret this as a task effect: in the 2-Object Condition, the disjunction plausibly encourages exclusive readings (i.e., 'A or B' implies 'not A and B'). In contrast, the presence of additional, unmentioned items (C, D) in the 4-Object Condition introduces alternative possibilities that weaken exclusivity inferences, instead promoting ad hoc reasoning (e.g., 'A or B' implies 'not C, not D'). Given that high exclusivity rates were previously observed with a similar guessing mode task, we attribute the lower rates here, at least in part, to the presence of additional objects in the visual background.

⁷Crucially, we chose a 4-Object design intentionally. Prior work (Huang and Crain 2020; Skordos et al. 2020) has shown that presenting only two objects can artificially inflate conjunctive interpretations in children, given that they either fail to consider plausible dissent (i.e., other possible situations where it could be false) or they consider the disjunctive utterance uninformative, and, consequently, default to conjunction. To avoid this potential confound, we followed previous studies in including additional objects beyond those mentioned in the utterances.

Such reasoning finds some support in the results of Huang and Crain (2020), who also included additional objects in the background (other than those mentioned in the disjunctive statements) and observed a relatively high rate of inclusivity in adults (around 42%). In contrast, a study like Tieu et al. (2017) had materials that only pictured the objects mentioned in the disjunctive utterance, and reported an inclusivity rate of only 15% in adults.⁸

Additionally, another factor that might have contributed to the low exclusivity rates observed in our study is the fact that participants were not exposed to the stronger conjunctive alternative in the course of the experiment (unlike in Goro and Akiba 2004, for instance, where participants were exposed to both disjunction and conjunction). As shown by Foppolo et al. (2012) for quantifiers, access to the stronger alternative may lead to more implicatures, although, as argued by Skordos and Papafragou (2016), the relevance of the alternative might ultimately play a more important role. We also note that in several experiments conducted on Romanian-speaking adults and children (Bleotu et al. 2024a, 2025a), where participants were exposed to both disjunction and conjunction, mere access to the conjunctive alternative *without relevance* did not seem to lead to more implicatures. Nonetheless, it is worth pointing out that the experiments in Bleotu et al. (2025a) targeted prosodically marked *sau* and the complex disjunctions *sau . . . sau* and *fie . . . fie*, and it remains unknown how participants might interpret the prosodically neutral *sau* in the presence of the conjunctive alternative.

Finally, it is possible that exposure to both positive and negative disjunctive utterances within the same experiment may have influenced participants' interpretations. For example, the preference for no strengthening in the negative condition may have made participants less likely to rely on strengthening in the positive condition as well. This explanation, however, seems less plausible in light of Cocharad et al.'s (2023) finding that French adults were exclusive, despite being exposed to both positive and negative disjunctive statements.

6.2. The interpretation of negative disjunctive statements

Turning to the negative disjunctive statements, our results suggest that *neither nor* is the preferred interpretation across the two age groups: both Romanian children and adults generally responded on the basis of the *neither nor* interpretation of negative disjunctive statements, rather than the *not both* or *only one* interpretation. Assuming that children start out with the logical interpretation of disjunction by default offers a fitting explanation for our overall findings. On the one hand, it explains children's *neither nor* interpretation in negative disjunctive contexts, as disjunction under negation is logically equivalent to the *neither nor* interpretation.⁹ On the other hand, it accounts for their inclusivity in positive disjunctive utterances. Importantly, the fact that a significant number of children preferred the *neither nor* interpretation is also consistent with the Semantic Subset Principle as formulated in Crain et al. (1994) and Goro (2007). In particular, Goro (2007) assumes the interpretation where negation c-commands disjunction to be the default, because it yields the strongest interpretation of a negative disjunctive statement – in line with our findings. However, Goro's formulation of the principle makes no particular predictions about children's behavior in positive contexts, given that it is a principle that targets negative disjunctive statements.

Alternatively, children's and adults' behavior in negative sentences could potentially be explained under a version of the Strongest Meaning Hypothesis (Dalrymple et al. 1998), which favors strong over weak meanings of ambiguous sentences. However, while assuming the strongest interpretation as

⁸It is nevertheless worth noting that the rate of inclusivity seems to be higher in Romanian (around 94%) than in Mandarin (42%), the language tested in Huang and Crain (2020). This difference could reflect language-specific factors: for example, Romanian has a rich inventory of complex disjunctions, which may be more readily associated with exclusive interpretations. In contrast, simple disjunctions such as *sau* could be more strongly associated with inclusive readings.

⁹One explanation for this interpretation is related to the fact that scalar implicatures are known to arise less frequently in negative or downward-entailing contexts (Chierchia 2004; Panizza et al. 2009a, 2009b; Panizza and Chierchia 2011). This means that participants will access a literal *neither nor* interpretation, with disjunction in the scope of negation, rather than parsing the sentence as NEG > EXH > OR, which would correspond to strengthening under negation (leading to the *either neither or both* reading).

a default would account for children's behavior in negative disjunctive statements, it would predict strong meanings in the positive cases as well (either exclusive or conjunctive), contrary to our findings.

Interestingly, for both groups, some participants were also able to access a *not both* interpretation in addition to the *neither nor* one. Negative disjunctive sentences thus exhibit some interpretive variability both in child and adult Romanian, as also reported in Lungu et al. (2021) for adults. Our adult findings stand in contrast, however, to the (slight) preference for the *not both* interpretation of disjunction reported in Lungu et al. (2021) and Lică (2024). This could be due to the different nature of the tasks: ours was a picture-based task, providing a more neutral context without explicit pragmatic cues. In contrast, their tasks were purely linguistic and actively manipulated the context to encourage different interpretations of negative disjunctive utterances.

Additionally, our study relied on a TVJT in Prediction Mode, where participants judged statements after already seeing the outcome. As pointed out by a reviewer, the fact that participants have to judge the statements after the uncertainty they imply is no longer present may make disjunctions slightly pragmatically odd, even if the disjunction is natural at the moment the puppet utters it. In contrast, the Uncertainty Mode assumed in Lungu et al. (2021) and Lică (2024), as well as in Goro (2017), presents the test sentences as uttered based on incomplete information, preserving pragmatic felicity.

Another important difference between our study and the previous ones is that in our study, participants were exposed to both positive and negative sentences. The contrast between positive and negative sentences might have influenced participants, leading them to draw a contrast in the possible interpretations of the disjunction. For instance, this contrast might have led them to associate negative disjunctive statements with the strong *neither nor* interpretation, which crucially is not compatible with the positive sentence, unlike the *only one* and *not both* interpretations.

Finally, yet another possible explanation for the difference between our study and the previous ones could be that Lică (2024) exposed participants not only to negative disjunctive statements containing *sau* 'or', but also to negative disjunctive statements containing *nici ... nici* 'neither ... nor'. The contrast between the two forms could have affected participants' responses, making them associate *nici ... nici* with a *neither nor* interpretation, the only possible interpretation for this construction, and *nu ... sau* with a *not both* interpretation.

The observed variability in possible interpretations of negative disjunctive statements suggests that the effect of the task is considerable and that the presence of alternative structures (positive vs. negative) or functional elements (*nici ... nici* vs. *nu ... sau*) can play a role in which interpretations are preferred by participants. The possible explanations we have provided for differences across studies are of course speculative. Future research could include more targeted, cross-linguistic investigations.

The fact that some Romanian speakers allow both the *not both* reading and the *neither nor* reading of negative disjunctive statements is particularly noteworthy. While Lungu et al. (2021) and Lică (2024) report similar findings, our study further underscores the importance of this apparent ambiguity, as it directly challenges the predictions made by the parametric account of disjunction, specifically the classification of Romanian as a [-PPI] language. This classification fails to account for the variability observed in our data, which shows that both the *not both* and *neither* readings are accessible to Romanian adults and children. Consequently, our findings suggest that a more nuanced approach to disjunction is necessary, one that goes beyond the binary classification of the [\pm PPI] framework.

Finally, the fact that the *not both* interpretation was less preferred than the *neither nor* interpretation (in both children and adults) may suggest that the *not both* interpretation requires more pragmatic support. Jing (2008) shows, for instance, that although English-speaking children typically prefer the *neither nor* reading, they can access the *not both* reading when the context supports it – such as when this meaning is made salient, disambiguating cues are present, contrasting forms are present, or when pragmatic training is provided. Thus, the *not both* interpretation may be dispreferred (in Romanian and other languages) not due to a lack of grammatical representation, but due to pragmatic factors.

6.3. No positive correlation between ‘neither nor’ and conjunctivity: Scope versus strengthening

We initially identified the hypothesis that there may exist a positive correlation between the *neither nor* interpretation of negative disjunctive statements and the conjunctive interpretation of positive disjunctive statements. The findings of the current study do not support this hypothesis. The children who displayed strong interpretations of negative disjunctive statements did not access strong interpretations of positive disjunctive statements. In fact, the majority (10/14) of the children who displayed the *neither nor* interpretation of negative disjunctive statements were inclusive rather than conjunctive for the positive disjunctive statements. This is not in line with the idea that children are using the same strengthening mechanism in the positive and negative contexts. Instead, the data suggest that, similarly to adults, in positive disjunctive statements, children are logical in their interpretation, hence inclusive, whereas in negative disjunctive sentences they adopt the *neither nor* interpretation by virtue of taking negation to scope over the disjunction. Our findings thus contradict a strengthening account and are overall more in line with the scope account proposed by Goro and Akiba (2004).

These findings have important implications for theories of language acquisition, suggesting that for negative disjunctive statements, children initially compute meanings based on structural properties, such as the scope of disjunction with respect to negation, rather than relying on pragmatic enrichment. This supports the idea that children are equipped with the tools to build scope-based interpretations early on, and that observed difficulties may lie more in pragmatic derivation.

Our findings differ from those of Cochard et al. (2023), who found evidence that French-speaking children who were conjunctive with positive disjunctive statements accessed the *neither nor* interpretation of negative disjunctive statements. This led them to conclude that children with a [+PPI] setting for the Disjunction Parameter and with no access to the conjunctive alternative rely on recursive exhaustification in both positive and negative disjunctive statements. Cochard et al. (2023) also found that a considerable number of children who interpreted negative disjunctive statements as *neither nor* were either exclusive with positive disjunctive statements (a large number) or inclusive. This pattern of responses can be captured by assuming a [-PPI] value for the disjunction parameter (leading to a NOT>OR reading), such that the strong interpretation of negated disjunctions is obtained differently from that of positive disjunctions. Thus, for Cochard et al. (2023), children’s interpretations of positive and negative disjunctive statements represent an interplay between the type of scope reading assumed and whether strengthening (with/without access to the stronger conjunctive alternative) applies. For Cochard et al. (2023), children’s conjunctive and inclusive interpretations of positive disjunctive statements stem from the failure to retrieve alternatives (either the conjunctive alternative or the pre-exhaustified disjunct alternatives). The *neither nor* reading may thus have two potential sources: a NOT>OR reading, or an OR>NOT reading with exhaustification over the pre-exhaustified disjunct alternatives. Importantly, though, if a child lacks the stronger alternative, this will be the case uniformly in both positive and negative contexts. Cochard et al.’s (2023) findings seem to support such a view, assuming some variability in the value for the PPI parameter among participants. In contrast, our Romanian findings are more in line with the NOT>OR source of *neither nor* readings, given that very few children were conjunctive in positive contexts.

Our conclusion that children’s *neither nor* interpretation relies on the NOT>OR reading is also in line with recent studies such as Otani et al. (2020), who investigated the role of the number of alternatives in the experimental set-up of negative disjunctive statements, and Shimada and Goro (2020), who investigated the role of syntactic position in the interpretation

of negative disjunctive statements. Crucially, these authors also argue in favor of a scope account and against a strengthening account of the *neither nor* interpretation.¹⁰

6.4. A developmental trajectory for negative disjunctive statements

The fact that children accessed both the *neither nor* and the *not both* interpretations of negative disjunctive statements (albeit with a clear preference for the former) raises important questions about how these readings are acquired. This preference seems to reflect a developmental trajectory in which children initially adopt the *neither nor* reading (for a couple of possible reasons which we discuss below), and only later develop the possibility of both scope interpretations. Given this pattern, one might hypothesize that children's and adults' grammars initially differ, given that children are limited to a narrower range of interpretations compared to adults. On such an approach, the 5-year-old children in our study may already be beyond the initial stage, where only the *neither nor* interpretation is available, which could explain why we also see responses in line with the *not both* interpretation. This suggests that by age five, children may already be in a transitional phase where both interpretations are accessible, although they may still show a preference for the *neither nor* reading.

Alternatively, it is possible that both interpretations are grammatically available from the start, but that pragmatic factors affect their accessibility. Applying a Continuity Assumption view (see Pinker 1984; Musolino and Lidz 2003), child and adult grammars would not differ qualitatively with respect to the interpretation of negation and disjunction: the fundamental grammatical structures available to both children and adults would be the same. However, children may process and access these structures more slowly or less consistently due to cognitive or developmental factors.

Let us briefly consider two possible explanations for the initial adherence to the *neither nor* interpretation. One possible explanation lies in the Subset Principle we discussed previously (Goro 2007): children would initially access only the reading on which negation scopes over disjunction, which yields the stronger of the possible interpretations (i.e., the *neither nor* reading). On the other hand, the *neither nor* preference might reflect a preference for isomorphic interpretations: the *neither nor* reading is the one on which the relative scope of negation and disjunction is aligned with the linear word order (with negation both preceding and syntactically scoping over the disjunction). Various studies (e.g., Musolino 1998; Musolino et al. 2000; Musolino and Lidz 2003) suggest that isomorphism does play a role in children's interpretations.¹¹ Importantly, in the case of the interaction between negation and disjunction, linear order does not conflict with the strongest interpretation, since the isomorphic order also corresponds to the strongest *neither nor* reading. Thus, it is difficult to determine whether children's preference for *neither nor* arises from isomorphism or from a preference for the strongest meaning. While it may be argued that isomorphism (also) plays a role in interpretation, evidence from English (Crain 2012) and Japanese (Shimada and Goro 2020) suggests that the c-command relation between negation and disjunction is a more likely explanation than linear order. In Crain et al. (2002), English-speaking children distinguished between sentences such as (15a) and (15b):

¹⁰Given that the *neither nor* interpretation appears to be scope-based, the findings raise the question of whether strengthening is needed to account for conjunctive interpretations of disjunction, when they do arise (this interpretation was extremely rare in our study for the disjunction *sau*). A potential alternative, which would support a strengthening-free account of strong disjunctive readings in both positive and negative contexts, would be to assume that the conjunctive interpretation stems from a conjunctive default rather than recursive exhaustification. For instance, Sauerland and Yatsushiro (2018) argue that disjunction is ambiguous between an inclusive and a conjunctive reading, while Aloni et al. (2024) and Bleotu et al. (2025a) propose that the conjunctive meaning reflects a default, with children initially assigning a conjunctive interpretation to disjunctive utterances. These alternative accounts warrant further investigation.

¹¹It is worth noting, however, that children's isomorphism bias may be overridden in certain cases, such as when the non-isomorphic interpretation is stronger than the isomorphic one. One such example from Romanian lies in 5-year-old children's interpretation of negated modals such as *nu e nevoie să* 'not is necessary SBJV', i.e., 'there's no need to' (see Bleotu, Benz, et al. 2023a): children interpret this as an interdiction ('must not'), although with an isomorphism bias, they would be predicted to interpret it as expressing lack of necessity, given that the negation both precedes and scopes over the necessity modal.

- (15) (a) The girl who stayed up late will **not** get a dime **or** a jewel.
 (b) The girl who didn't go to sleep will get a dime **or** a jewel.

Contrary to what a purely linear order account would predict, they only interpreted (15a) as *neither nor*, given that only in this context does negation c-command disjunction. Moreover, Shimada and Goro (2020) show that Japanese-speaking children vary their interpretation of the disjunction marker *ka* depending on its syntactic position, even though both subjects and objects precede negation in Japanese, an SOV language. These findings cannot be captured by a simple linear order account, indicating that additional syntactic and semantic factors must be involved.

Returning to our assumptions about the developmental trajectory, regardless of whether we assume that children's initial grammar is the same as that of adults (the Continuity view) or not (the Subset view), there remain learnability challenges to be overcome, given the limited availability of utterances involving negation and disjunction in the input. Moreover, our data do not allow us to definitively tease these views apart, as both adults and children preferred the *neither nor* interpretation, while also allowing the *not both* interpretation. Nonetheless, at face value, the data appear to support a continuity view, given the observed similarity between the adult and child behavior. Further studies should investigate the interpretation of negation and disjunction in younger children – around age three, for instance – to determine whether younger children exhibit more consistent access to the *neither nor* reading, and whether a gradual developmental shift toward the possibility of the *not both* interpretation can be observed with age. Such evidence would help establish whether the *neither nor* interpretation represents a default in the early grammar.

Finally, it may be that the answers in line with the *not both* interpretation can be explained by priming effects within the experiment, creating the expectation that the animal character will act in some way rather than fail to act at all. Throughout the task, the test items involved two conditions where the animal character carried out an action (a condition where the animal acted upon one object, and a condition where the animal acted upon two objects), but only one condition where the animal character did not carry out any action at all. The greater number of situations involving an action on the part of the animal character may have led children away from the *neither nor* interpretation toward the *not both* interpretation.

6.5. Limitations and future directions

While our study has the advantage of collecting data pertaining to both positive and negative disjunctive statements from the same set of participants, it also has some limitations. Notably, both positive and negative disjunctive statements count as guesses that the puppet makes and which participants then have to evaluate as good or bad. However, it may be argued that positive guesses are more natural and likely than negative guesses by default, and, consequently, negative guesses such as *The giraffe did not pick the snowdrop or the rose* may be perceived as pragmatically odd. To make such utterances pragmatically felicitous, one would need to accommodate them in the context, for instance, by introducing a negative question (such as *What didn't the giraffe do?*).

Importantly, Sano et al. (2024) have recently shown that if the experiment takes into consideration the Question Under Discussion (QUD) by introducing negative questions and by manipulating the visual background (showing participants what was NOT the case), even Japanese-speaking children, who have otherwise been claimed to access only the *neither nor* interpretation (Goro and Akiba 2004), will show evidence of the weaker *not both* interpretation.¹²

¹²As pointed out by an anonymous reviewer, while the observations made by Sano et al. (2024) are certainly insightful, some caution is warranted regarding the generalizability of their findings. Notably, they tested the conjunction *mo . . . mo* with a different group of participants, using a between-subjects design, which could lead to differences in behavior compared to a within-subjects design.

For this reason, we believe a worthwhile future extension of the current study should involve testing the same children for their interpretation of negative and positive disjunctive statements in contexts that introduce negative and positive QUDs, respectively. In this manner, one can ensure that the answers provided by children (and adults) are due to their genuine understanding of disjunctive statements, rather than due to any potential pragmatic infelicity.

Another possible concern might be that exposing children to both positive and negative disjunctive statements may have influenced their interpretation. For instance, had children not been exposed to positive disjunctive statements, many more of them might have displayed the *neither nor* interpretation. For this reason, future studies could investigate how children's interpretation changes when positive and negative statements are tested separately, in different experimental sessions rather than within the same session.

7. Conclusion

Our study showed that Romanian 5-year-olds and adults tend to prefer strong *neither nor* interpretations of negative disjunctive statements, though some of them also seem to access a weaker *not both* interpretation, displaying more variability in their responses. We discussed various possible explanations for participants' preference for the strong *neither nor* interpretation, including a preference for stronger meanings, adherence to a Semantic Subset Principle, syntactic scope, and isomorphism. The finding that the *not both* interpretation is nevertheless available to some adult and child participants raises questions about the simple classification of Romanian as a [+PPI] language.

Importantly, by collecting data from the same participants for both positive and negative disjunctive statements, our study also addressed the question of whether children who have strong interpretations of negative disjunctive statements are the same ones who display strong interpretations of positive disjunctive statements, and if so, whether such a correlation may be due to such children consistently relying on the same strengthening mechanism across polarities. Our findings do not support such a relationship, as most *neither nor* children were otherwise inclusive in positive contexts. Rather, a more likely source for *neither nor* interpretations is the narrow scope of disjunction with respect to negation.

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Credit authorship contribution statement

Adina Camelia Bleotu: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Visualization, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Project administration, Resources, Writing – original draft, Writing - review & editing; **Lyn Tieu:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Visualization, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing; **Gabriela Bilbiie:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing; **Mara Panaitescu:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – review & editing; **Anton Benz:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing; **Andreea Cristina Nicolae:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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ORCID

Adina Camelia Bleotu <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-5838-2676>
 Lyn Tieu <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-2794-7977>
 Gabriela Bilbiie <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-4547-1645>
 Mara Panaitescu <http://orcid.org/0009-0003-0631-9557>
 Anton Benz <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-1128-6636>
 Andreea Cristina Nicolae <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-7737-5009>

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Ethics and consent

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Data availability statement

The data and scripts for the statistical analyses are available on OSF (https://osf.io/v9wt4/?view_only=2adb96956b7547d19acbed72552d4e75).

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Appendix A

Table A1: Procedure for negative disjunctive utterances in the 1DT condition

1DT

SCENE 1: There once was a zebra that sometimes carried groceries and sometimes did not. One day, she went shopping with her mom. The zebra's mom bought fruits and vegetables: a tomato, a grape, a banana, a carrot. The zebra could choose to carry a fruit, she could choose to carry several, she could choose to carry nothing.

Let's see if Bibi can guess what happened next!

SCENE 2:

EXPERIMENTER: Bibi, tell us, what happened next?

BIBI: *Zebra nu a cărat banana sau morcovul.*

'The zebra did not carry the banana or the carrot.'

EXPERIMENTER: Let's see if Bibi's right!

SCENE 3 (following seeing a picture where the zebra is carrying a banana:

Look, the zebra carried this! Did Bibi guess well?

Pictures

Table A2: Procedure for negative disjunctive utterances in the ODT condition

ODT

SCENE 1: There once was a koala who sometimes ate food he received and sometimes did not. Koala received some food on his birthday. He could choose a dish to eat, he could choose several dishes, he could choose nothing. Let's see if Bibi can guess what happened next!

SCENE 2:

EXPERIMENTER: Bibi, tell us, what happened next?

BIBI: *Koala nu a cules prăjitura sau salata.*

'Koala did not choose the cake or the salad.'

EXPERIMENTER: Let's see if Bibi's right!

SCENE 3 (following seeing a picture where Koala chose nothing): Look, he did not choose the cake, he did not choose the salad! Did Bibi guess well?

Pictures

